

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE OF EXCLUSIVE BREASTFEEDING AMONG MOTHERS

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Abstract

Objective: "To determine the frequency of mothers having good knowledge, positive attitude and adherent practice about breastfeeding."

Study Design: Cross sectional study.

Study place and duration: Department of Pediatrics, Avicenna Medical College & Hospital, Lahore for about 3 months (5 March 2025 till 5 June 2025)

Methodology: Mothers fulfilled the inclusion criteria were enrolled from Pediatric OPD. A face-to-face interview was done and data was recorded in pre-designed questionnaire. Questionnaire contained questions assessing knowledge, attitudes and practices towards breastfeeding among mothers and responses were noted.

Results: In this study, 147 mothers of mean age 28.62 ± 6.80 years were enrolled with 66 (44.9%) male and 81 (55.1%) female neonates. The mean knowledge score was 5.50 ± 1.38 . On the basis of those 107 (74.1%) mothers had good knowledge about breastfeeding. The mean attitude score was noted as 2.93 ± 1.22 . On the basis of those 117 (79.6%) mothers had positive attitude towards breastfeeding. The mean practice score was noted as 2.56 ± 1.07 . On the basis of those 79 (53.7%) mothers had adherent practice towards breastfeeding.

Conclusion: It is concluded that in local population, more than 70% mothers had good knowledge and positive attitude towards breastfeeding. But still there is a need to improve the knowledge to further improve the practice of breastfeeding.

INTRODUCTION

Early beginning of breastfeeding is defined as starting to breastfeed within 60 minutes after the baby's birth. By WHO and UNICEF.^{1, 2} Breastfeeding should begin as soon as feasible to increase survival chances. According to international data, half of newborns, or around 80 million babies, are not breastfed within the first hour of their lives.^{3, 4}

Children under the age of five who are not breastfed have higher rates of illness and death. 50% of deaths in children under five occur during the neonatal period, and this can be somewhat avoided by breastfeeding the newborn. Numerous studies on breastfeeding have shown that it is good for both the mother's health and the health of her newborn

children.^{5, 6} Because breast milk has more whey protein and less protein overall, it is also less immunogenic. Breast milk ensures the best possible establishment of microbiological flora, which protects against disorders of the gastrointestinal system. Additionally, breast milk possesses immunomodulating properties that guarantee a newborn's proper immune response when exposed to an antigen or microbiological pathogen.^{7, 8}

The practice still appears to be unpromising despite significant recommendations in favor of exclusive breastfeeding. The National Family Health Survey-Round 4 shows that only 54.9% of infants between the ages of 0 and 6 months are exclusively breastfed.⁹ Numerous factors, including family pressures, the mother's education, sociocultural traditions, maternal age, family income, socioeconomic status, family size, site of delivery, and the timing of initial breastfeeding start, impact knowledge and attitudes about exclusive breastfeeding. In addition to breast milk, the majority of non-exclusively breastfed children also eat milk, water, formula, or supplemental foods, which frequently results in illnesses in hazardous settings.^{10, 11} The rationale of this study is to determine KAP of mother toward breastfeeding in local population. Very little information is known about the factors that influence nursing moms' decision to exclusively breastfeed. Therefore, it is essential to investigate these issues. In light of this, the current study was designed to investigate postpartum moms' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors about breastfeeding in our community.

METHODOLOGY

This Cross sectional study was conducted at Department of Pediatrics, Avicenna Medical College & Hospital, Lahore for around 3 months (5 March 2025 till 5 June 2025). Sample size was calculated using WHO calculator keeping 95% confidence interval, 8% absolute precision and adherent practice in 42.7% mothers.¹² Sample size will 147 mother. Mothers who fulfilled the following criteria were enrolled by applying Non probability consecutive sampling technique.

Inclusion Criteria:

Mothers of healthy neonates and infants aged 1 month to 2 years who were being breast fed and children born between 37 and 42 weeks of gestation were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

Mothers of preterm babies, multiple gestations, mothers who did not give consent and mother of babies having congenital anomalies and congenital malformation were excluded.

After approval from hospital ethical board, mothers were enrolled from Pediatric OPD. A written informed consent was taken after explaining the purpose of study. A face to face interview of study participants was done for collection of data in a separate room. A pre-designed structured questionnaire was used to collect the data. It consisted of two parts; first part had questions eliciting information about the demographic profile of participants: Age of baby, gender of baby, type of family, working status of mothers, educational level of mother, monthly income of family and place of delivery of baby. The second part contained questions assessing knowledge, attitudes and practices towards breastfeeding among mothers. The questions were asked in a local language and the time taken to complete the questionnaire was approximately between 15-20 minutes. After the completion of interview, all the mothers were informed about the significance of prolonged breast feeding up to period of 2 years. For knowledge 7 question was asked having answers in yes or no forms. Mothers giving correct answers of 5 or more questions was labelled as having good knowledge. For attitude 4 questions was asked having answers in yes or no forms. Mothers giving correct answers of 2 or more questions was labelled as having positive attitude toward breast feeding. For practice 5 questions was asked. Mothers giving correct answers of 3 or more questions was labelled as adherent practice towards breast feeding. Confidentiality of participants was assured and maintained. Data was entered in specially designed proforma.

Data will be entered and analyzed by using SPSS version 22.0. Knowledge, Attitude and Practice towards breastfeeding were presented as frequency and percentage. Effect modifiers like age, gender,

type of family, working status of mothers, educational level of mother, monthly income of family and place of delivery of baby were addressed through stratification. Post-stratification, chi-square was applied to compare stratified groups for Knowledge, Attitude and Practice towards breastfeeding. P value ≤ 0.05 was taken as significant.

RESULTS

In this study, 147 mothers of mean age 28.62 ± 6.80 years were enrolled with 66 (44.9%) male and 81 (55.1%) female neonates. Out of 147 mothers, 67 (45.6%) mothers were living as nuclear family while 80 (54.4%) were living in combined family system. There were 46 (31.3%) mothers who were illiterate, 28 (19.0%) had education up to matric, 32 (21.8%) up to intermediate while 41 (27.9%) were graduate. More than half of the mothers [76 (51.7%)] were working ladies. More than 90% deliveries were done in hospital setting. Table-I

The mean knowledge score was 5.50 ± 1.38 . On the basis of those 107 (74.1%) mothers had good knowledge about breastfeeding while 38 (25.9%) had poor knowledge. The mean attitude score was noted as 2.93 ± 1.22 . On the basis of those 117 (79.6%) mothers had positive attitude towards breastfeeding while 30 (20.4%) had negative attitude. The mean practice score was noted as 2.56 ± 1.07 . On the basis of that 79 (53.7%) mothers had adherent practice towards breastfeeding while 68 (46.3%) were not practicing breastfeeding. Table-II

Data was stratified for mother’s age, family type, mothers’ education, and occupation. It was observed that mother’s age has no impact on good knowledge about breastfeeding (61 (80.3%) vs. 48 (67.6%), p-value = 0.080) in females aged 18-29 years or 30-40 years old. Similarly, mothers living alone had almost similar knowledge as mothers living in combined family system (49 (73.1%) vs. 60 (75.0%), p-value = 0.797). Mothers whose education is graduate or

above had better knowledge about breastfeeding [33 (80.5%)] than less educated mothers, and most of the mother with less education had poor knowledge about breastfeeding, although the difference was insignificant (p-value = 0.178). Similar, chances of good knowledge are better with working ladies [58 (76.3%)] as compared to housewives [51 (71.8%)], although the difference was insignificant (p-value = 0.555). Table-III

It was observed that mother’s age has no impact on positive attitude about breastfeeding (63 (82.9%) vs. 54 (76.1%), p-value =0.304) in females aged 18-29 years or 30-40 years old. Similarly, mothers living in combined family system had more chances of positive attitude [67 (83.8%)] towards breastfeeding than mothers living alone [50 (74.6%)], although the difference was insignificant (p-value = 0.172). Mothers whose education is matric or above had positive attitude about breastfeeding [more than 80%] than illiterate mothers, although the difference was insignificant (p-value = 0.459). Similar, chances of positive attitude are better with housewives [58 (81.7%)] as compared to working ladies [59 (77.6%)], although the difference was insignificant (p-value = 0.452). Table-IV

It was observed that mother’s age has no impact on adherent practice about breastfeeding (41 (53.9%) vs. 38 (53.5%), p-value =0.959) in females aged 18-29 years or 30-40 years old. Similarly, mothers either living alone or in combined family system had almost similar adherent practice [37 (55.2%) vs. 42 (52.5%), p-value = 0.741]. Mothers whose education is graduate or above had better adherent practice [26 (63.4%)] than mothers with less education [more than 50%] or illiterate [21 (45.7%)], although the difference was insignificant (p-value = 0.430). Similar, chances of adherent practice are better with working ladies [45 (59.2%)] as compared to housewives [34 (47.9%)], although the difference was insignificant (p-value = 0.169). Table-V

Table-I: demographics details of neonates and their mothers (n = 147)

Parameter	Output
Mother’s age (years)	28.62 ± 6.80
Gender of neonates	
Male / Female	66 (44.9%) / 81 (55.1%)

Type of family system	
Nuclear / Combined	67 (45.6%) / 80 (54.4%)
Mother's education level	
Illiterate	46 (31.3%)
Matric	28 (19.0%)
Intermediate	32 (21.8%)
Graduate	41 (27.9%)
Mother's occupation	
Working lady / House wife	76 (51.7%) / 71 (48.3%)
Place of delivery	
Home / Hospital	13 (8.8%) / 134 (91.2%)

Table-II: Knowledge, attitude and practice of mothers towards breastfeeding (n = 147)

Parameter	Output
Knowledge score	5.50 ± 1.38
Good Knowledge	107 (74.1%)
Poor Knowledge	38 (25.9%)
Attitude score	2.93 ± 1.22
Positive attitude	117 (79.6%)
Negative attitude	30 (20.4%)
Practice score	2.56 ± 1.07
Adherent practice	79 (53.7%)
Not practicing	68 (46.3%)

Table-III: Association of good knowledge with maternal characteristics (n = 147)

		Good knowledge		p-value
		Yes (n = 109)	No (n = 38)	
Mother's age (years)	18-29	61 (80.3%)	15 (19.7%)	0.080
	30-40	48 (67.6%)	23 (32.4%)	
Family type	Nuclear	49 (73.1%)	18 (26.9%)	0.797
	Combined	60 (75.0%)	20 (25.0%)	
Mother's education	Illiterate	36 (78.3%)	10 (21.7%)	0.178
	Matric	21 (75.0%)	7 (25.0%)	
	Intermediate	19 (59.4%)	13 (40.6%)	
	Graduate	33 (80.5%)	8 (19.5%)	
Occupation	Working lady	58 (76.3%)	18 (23.7%)	0.555
	Housewife	51 (71.8%)	20 (28.2%)	

Table-IV: Association of positive attitude with maternal characteristics (n = 147)

		Positive attitude		p-value
		Yes (n = 117)	No (n = 30)	
Mother's age (years)	18-29	63 (82.9%)	13 (17.1%)	0.304
	30-40	54 (76.1%)	17 (23.9%)	
Family type	Nuclear	50 (74.6%)	17 (25.4%)	0.172

	Combined	67 (83.8%)	13 (16.3%)	
Mother's education	Illiterate	33 (71.7%)	13 (28.3%)	0.459
	Matric	23 (82.1%)	5 (17.9%)	
	Intermediate	27 (84.4%)	5 (15.6%)	
	Graduate	34 (82.9%)	7 (17.1%)	
Occupation	Working lady	59 (77.6%)	17 (22.4%)	0.542
	Housewife	58 (81.7%)	13 (18.3%)	

Table-V: Association of positive attitude with maternal characteristics (n = 147)

		Adherent practice		p-value
		Yes (n = 79)	No (n = 68)	
Mother's age (years)	18-29	41 (53.9%)	35 (46.1%)	0.959
	30-40	38 (53.5%)	33 (46.5%)	
Family type	Nuclear	37 (55.2%)	30 (44.8%)	0.741
	Combined	42 (52.5%)	38 (47.5%)	
Mother's education	Illiterate	21 (45.7%)	25 (54.3%)	0.430
	Matric	15 (53.6%)	13 (46.4%)	
	Intermediate	17 (53.1%)	15 (46.9%)	
	Graduate	26 (63.4%)	15 (36.6%)	
Occupation	Working lady	45 (59.2%)	31 (40.8%)	0.169
	Housewife	34 (47.9%)	37 (52.1%)	

DISCUSSION

In our study, we observed the mean knowledge score of 5.50 ± 1.38 . On the basis of that 107 (74.1%) mothers had good knowledge about breastfeeding. The mean attitude score was noted as 2.93 ± 1.22 and about 117 (79.6%) mothers had positive attitude towards breastfeeding. The mean practice score was noted as 2.56 ± 1.07 and about 79 (53.7%) mothers had adherent practice towards breastfeeding.

Bala et al., carried out a survey in newly delivered mothers and observed that about 95.5% mother had good knowledge of breastfeeding, positive attitude towards breastfeeding was found in 50% mothers and breastfeeding practice was adopted by 42.7% mothers.¹² Temoirokomalani et al., cross-sectional study on 415 mothers and observed that more than 95% had good knowledge about breastfeeding, More than 50% mothers had positive attitude towards breastfeeding while more than 90% mothers were practicing breastfeeding.¹³

Murtaza et al., conducted a cross sectional survey in Azad Kashmir and found that about 80.9% mothers were well aware of exclusive breastfeeding, 65.2% mothers had positive attitude, while about 62.9%

mothers had unsatisfactory breast-feeding practice. Researchers concluded that emotional support, maternal perceptions, outdoor working status, mother becoming pregnant again, mother being sick, and breast infection were the factors affecting breast-feeding continuation.¹⁴ Alia et al., demonstrated that the 81.1% of women thought that breastfeeding was more feasible than the other forms of feeding options for their children, indicating that the majority of mothers had a positive attitude toward the practice.¹⁵ Although Rudrappa et al., reported that the 70% of mothers were knowledgeable about colostrum feeding, however only 35% of respondents were knowledgeable about the duration of exclusive breastfeeding.¹⁶ In the study by Krishnendu et al., also stated that the 70.8% of breastfeeding women having average levels of knowledge, 55.5% had positive attitudes, and 79.2% seemed to have good breastfeeding practices.¹⁷

Jalil et al., performed a research on 200 moms in Malaysia and discovered that the majority of them had strong KAP: 87% had appropriate nursing practices, 75.5% had a positive attitude, and 72.5% had adequate knowledge.¹⁸ Kurian et al., noted that

respondents showed poor breastfeeding practices despite having a high level of knowledge and attitude, highlighting the necessity of breastfeeding intervention programs, particularly in the prenatal and early postpartum periods. Programs that now assist breastfeeding at the primary care level have to be reinforced. Family members should also receive behavior change communication in order to ensure that the proper breastfeeding practice is followed.¹⁹

In our study, we observed that good knowledge was noted more in working ladies (76.3%) as compared to housewives (71.8%), and more adherent practice among working ladies (59.2%) than housewives (47.9%), but positive attitude are better among housewives (81.7%), although the difference was insignificant (p-value >0.05). However, it has been noted in the past that breastfeeding behaviors are also influenced by the job situation of women. Importantly, compared to working women, even those who were still in school, jobless mothers were more likely to report using excellent breastfeeding methods.^{13, 20, 21} The results of the majority of research were in opposition to this one. According to a research conducted in the United Arab Emirates, housewives are more likely than working moms to exclusively breastfeed. Due to their need to return to work, the majority of moms discontinued nursing.²² Previous research showed that healthcare workers' motivation was a stronger predictor of knowledge increase, attitudes, and breastfeeding-friendly practices. It also showed that mothers require support and encouragement from the health system as well as from their families and communities in order to successfully initiate and continue breastfeeding.^{23, 24}

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that in local population, more than 70% mothers had good knowledge and positive attitude towards breastfeeding. But still there is a need to improve the knowledge to further improve the practice of breastfeeding. So counseling sessions and seminars can be conducted in order to improve the benefits of breastfeeding among young mothers and practice of breastfeeding can be improved.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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